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A blockchain-based architecture and smart contracts for an interoperable Physical Internet

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Abstract

1. Overview and motivation

The Physical Internet (PI) is an emerging T&L paradigm that can be defined as an open global logistics system founded on physical, digital, and operational interconnectivity through encapsulation, interfaces, and protocols [1]. It is driven by technological, infrastructural, and business innovation, hence the emergence of Blockchain and smart contracts and most importantly their application in modern T&L networks is highly intertwined with the evolution of the PI. Blockchain features and functionalities have the potential not only to meet PI implementation requirements but also to overcome key PI barriers and deficiencies [2]. Despite the advantages the PI may offer, it cannot continue relying on centralised networks nor on the existence of a leading authority [3]. In this manner, the PI will be able to proliferate only if follows a distributed and community driven concept and approach.

Especially smart contracts play an instrumental role in the roadmap towards the PI. The Alliance for Logistics Innovation through Collaboration in Europe (ALICE) has proclaimed that they can achieve this goal in two ways: by creating seamless booking systems to increase response time and by becoming proactive in the smart use of resources employing fully autonomous services and operations with predefined smart contracts [4].

However, T&L stakeholders have already joined Blockchain consortia and/or deployed their own private, permissioned networks through which they exchange information with their partners in a trustful manner, thus creating disconnected networks that are impossible to bridge. Blockchain interoperability is a chief enabler for the PI, as it offers the ability for existing disparate Blockchain systems to interoperate and share data regarding shipping manifests, smart contracts, customs declarations, transport events and so on. The interconnection of these silos is a challenge tackled by the proposed blueprint architecture, which is deployed in the PLANET project, but can also be replicated in other supply chains to increase visibility and enhance the collaboration among the participants.

2. Methodology, results and main contributions

The PLANET project proposes an open-source architectural blueprint to empower organisations to build and implement T&L design tools, collaborative logistics and new eCommerce models underpinned by data-driven supply chain insights. It also formalises a set of guidelines to facilitate the realisation of an EU–Global T&L Network (EGTN) Platform. The EGTN Platform architecture integrates T&L data from heterogeneous sources, such as smart logistics assets (smart pallets, smart containers, and smart warehouses), logistics time schedules, and weather news. Following that, it augments the data using Knowledge Graphs, and feeds them to other services such as AI predictive analytics, Decision Support Systems, and smart contracts, as well as to graphical interfaces for their visualisation. This paper describes the Blockchain and Data Aggregator components of the EGTN architecture which are employed together to enable interoperability between backend Blockchain systems hosted by different T&L stakeholders (Figure 1).

The main contributions include standardised interfaces that enable simple connection of Blockchain systems with the EGTN Blockchain service as well as standardised smart contracts rules to enhance transparency and visibility across the supply chain. The EGTN Smart Contracts listen for logistic events in the individual Blockchain networks and forward these to other Blockchain communities that can benefit from them by acting proactively and increasing

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response time.

The Data Aggregator provides an event-streaming service that ingests logistics events and IoT data from sensors, following the latest GS1 standards. The smart contracts consume data within the EGTN Platform, combine these with other information sources (e.g., outputs from AI predictive models), and automatically trigger actions, such as the creation of trusted metadata that can be used as a single source of truth in Blockchain communities or even the generation of new smart contracts that monitor and safeguard SLAs between logistic communities (e.g., carriers and freight forwarders).

Figure 1: EGTN Blockchain Frontend and Smart Contracts

3. Conclusion and future works

The solution offered by the PLANET project offers a distributed and community-driven approach that ensures data integrity and immutability across the supply chain, automated and safe contract execution, and reduction of overheads and time delays. In this manner, the value of Blockchain interoperability and smart contracts to the PI paradigm are showcased through the application of the solution in real-life use cases. It is expected that the deployment of the infrastructure in the demo sites of PLANET will bring out further insights and inform the architectural blueprint.

References

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